

"APPLICATION OF STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES IN DEMOGRAPHIC STUDIES: CORRELATION BETWEEN LITERACY AND SEX RATIO IN SOLAPUR DISTRICT"

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ABSTRACT:

Statistical techniques are useful in geographical studies for data analysis. Using these techniques we can suggest better conclusion in any region. This paper is an attempts to analysis the correlation between literacy and sex ratio in Solapur district. Literacy is one of the important indicators of social development which is depend on the education. As such, certain minimum level of literacy seems to essential for a population break and it also affected on migration and sex ratio. For the analysis the correlation between literacy and sex ratio of Solapur district Spearman's Rank order method used. The correlation between literacy and sex ratio in Solapur district is $r = -0.2923$. It means high literacy and low sex ratio.

KEY WORDS: Literacy, Sex ratio, spatial pattern, mental isolation, Demographic.

INTRODUCTION:

Literacy and sex ratio are the main demographic characteristics of population. Literacy rate plays vital role in upliftment of the sex ratio. Literacy is defined as the ability to read and write in any language. Now a days the concept of literacy is expanding across all countries to include to various skills. The modern term's meaning has been expanded to include the ability to use language, numbers, images and computers. According to census of India "a person aged more than six years and who can both read and write with understanding in any language has taken as a literate". The census of India defines the literacy rate as a proportion of literates to total population in age group seven years and above. Literacy is essential for eradicating poverty and mental isolation. Sex ratio is the ratio of males to females in a population. It is important indicator of human development. Sex ration also expressed in terms of number of female per thousand of males. According to 2011 census, the sex ratio of Maharashtra is 925 female per thousand male. In Maharashtra Ratnagiri district records highest sex ratio (1122 female per thousand male) and Mumbai has the lowest sex ratio (838 females per thousand male).

STUDY REGION:

Solapur district lies to the south western part of Maharashtra state which is the fifth largest district in terms of area and seventh largest in terms of population in Maharashtra. The Solapur

Fig No.1

district is located between 17°07' N to 18° 33' N latitudes and 74°37' E to 76°26' E longitudes. The average height of Solapur district from MSL varies from 500 to 800 meters. It is bounded by Sangli district to its southwest, Satara district to its west, Pune district to its northwest, Ahmadnagar district to its north, Osmanabad district to its east and Bijapur district in the Karnataka to the with south. The total geographical area of study region is 14,895 sq. km. with a population of 4,31,7756 according to 2011 census. For administrative purpose Solapur district is divided in to 11 tahsils i.e. Akkalkot, Barshi, Karmala, Madha, Malshiras, Mangalwedha, Mohol, North Solapur, Pandharpur, Sangola and South Solapur and constitutes 20 percent of the total geographical area of Pune division and 4.8 percent of the state of Maharashtra.

OBJECTIVES:

The major objectives of this paper are as under

1. To study the spatial pattern of literacy and sex ratio in the study region.
2. To analyze the correlation between literacy rate and sex ratio in the Solapur district.

DATABASE AND METHODOLOGY:

This paper is based on secondary sources of data. The data related to literacy and sex ratio of Solapur district is obtained from Census of Maharashtra (2011) and Statistical Abstract of Solapur district (2011). The collected data are processed to analyze the pattern of literacy and sex ratio in Solapur district. Arc GIS 10.3 Software used for preparing the map for showing spatial pattern of sex ratio and literacy in Solapur district. Using simple statistical method the tahsils of Solapur district grouped into High, Medium and Low categories. The Spearman's rank order method is used for analyzes the correlation between literacy and sex ratio.

Rank Order of Spearman's Method:

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

DISCUSSIONS:

A) Spatial Pattern of Sex ratio:

Solapur district as a whole has 932 number of females per thousand male population in 2011. But the tahsil level sex ratio varies from 914 to 960. The all tahsils are categorized in three groups as follows (Fig No.2).

- 1) **High Sex Ratio:** The tahsil which have sex ratio above 950 are included into high category. High sex ratio was recorded in Akkalkot tahsil. Due to maximum migration and less maternal mortality rate this tahsil recorded highest sex ratio in Solapur district in 2011.

Fig No. 2

Table No.1 Solapur District- Literacy Rate and Sex Ratio (2011)

Sr. No.	Name of Tahsil	Literacy % (X)	Sex Ratio (Y)	Rank (X)	Rank (Y)	D	(D) ²
1	Akkalkot	69.63	960	11	1	10	100
2	Barshi	78.93	929	2	7	-5	25
3	Karmala	75.52	927	7	8	-1	1
4	Madha	77.12	933	4	5.5	-1.5	2.25
5	Malshiras	76.63	937	5	4	1	1
6	Mangalwedha	72.25	925	10	10	0	0
7	Mohol	75.77	914	6	11	-5	25
8	North Solapur	82.07	942	1	2	-1	1
9	Pandharpur	77.68	926	3	9	-6	36
10	Sangola	72.89	933	9	5.5	3.5	12.25
11	South Solapur	73.42	941	8	3	5	25

Source: 1. Socio-Economic Review of Solapur District (2011)

2. STATISTICAL ABSTRACT OF SOLAPUR DISTRICT (2011)

2. **Moderate Sex Ratio:** The tahsils which have the sex ratio ranges from 930 to 950 are included into moderate category. Madha, Malshiras, Sangola, South Solapur and North Solapur tahsils are included in this category. There are some reasons for moderate sex ration in these tahsil i.e. minimum migration, better medical facilities and depend on agriculture and allied economic activities.

3. **Low Sex Ratio:** The tahsils which sex ratio has below 930 included into low sex ratio category. Mohol, Mangalwedha, Pandharpur, Karmala and Barshi tahsils are included in this category. Neglected of child girls, high maternal mortality and female infanticide are responsible for low sex ratio in these tahsils.

Fig No.3

B) Spatial Pattern of Literacy Rate:

Solapur district as a whole has 77.02 percent literacy rate in 2011. But the tahsil level literacy differs from ranging 69.63 percent to 82.07 percent. All these eleven tahsil of Solapur district are divided into three categories (fig No.4).

- 1) **High Literacy Rate:** The tahsil have literacy rate of 80 percent included in this category. North Solapur is one of the tahsil which included in this category because of better educational facilities, maximum number of educational institutions, high urbanization and development of transport and communication.
- 2) **Moderate Literacy Rate:** The tahsil which ranges between 75 to 80 percent included into moderate categories. Mohol, Pandharpur, Barshi, Karmala, Malshiras and Madha tahsil recorded moderate literacy rate in 2011. Moderate educational facilities and network accessibility are the main reason for moderate literacy rate. Excepting city in these tahsil all types of facilities are poor.

Fig No.4

3) **Low Sex Ratio Literacy Rate:** The literacy ratio below 75 percent included in this categories. There are four taluk including Akkalkot, South Solapur, Mangalwedha and Sangola which has recorded lowest sex ratio in Solapur district. Lack of educational facilities, poverty and drought area are the main reason of low sex ratio.

Correlation between literacy and sex ratio: The Spearman's rank order method is used for the calculation of literacy and sex ratio in Solapur district. It is observed that there is moderate negative correlation ($r = -0.2923$) between the literacy and sex ratio in Solapur district.

CONCLUSIONS:

There were wide disparities in the demographic factor of literacy rate and sex ratio in Solapur district in 2011. The highest literacy was found in North Solapur (82.07) taluk and lowest literacy in Akkalkot (69.63). The highest sex ratio is found in Akkalkot taluk (960) and lowest in Mohol taluk (914). But the correlation between literacy and sex ratio found in low degree and negative angle i.e. $r = -0.2923$. It means high literacy and low sex ratio.

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